

Thermodynamic Constants of Gallium (III) Chelates of Some Halo Derivatives of 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid

BALRAJ K. AVINASHI & SAMIR K. BANERJI

Chemical Laboratories, Birla Institute of Technology & Science, Pilani (Rajasthan)

Received 7 July 1971, revised MSS received 3 April 1972

Gallium(III) forms in aqueous medium, 1 : 3 chelates with 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (R_1) and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (R_2), both having λ max at 355 nm, stable in the pH ranges 3.3-7.6 and 2.9-5.9 respectively. The stability constants calculated by the mole-ratio method and the method using molecular extinction coefficient data have been found to be $\log K = 13.5 \pm 0.2$ and 13.6 ± 0.2 respectively for $Ga(R_1)_3$ and $Ga(R_2)_3$ chelates at 20°. The values of free energy of formation in these chelates come out to be $\Delta F = -18.1 \pm 0.3$ kcal/mole and -18.3 ± 0.3 kcal/mole at 20°. The enthalpy changes and entropy changes calculated by the temperature coefficient method and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation respectively are found to be 1.44 kcal/mole and 65.4 e.u. for the $Ga(R_1)_3$ chelate and 7.78 kcal/mole and 87.8 e.u. for the $Ga(R_2)_3$ chelate.

7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (R_1) and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (R_2), like their parent compound 8-quinolinol, act as very strong chelating agents. These ligands form water soluble complexes with a number of metal ions. The present study deals with the investigation of Gallium(III) chelates of 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid spectrophotometrically regarding composition, stability and thermodynamic parameters like ΔF , ΔH and ΔS , associated with the formation of these chelates in aqueous medium.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer (Model H 700.308) using 1 cm cell. The cell compartment was fitted with a jacket through which water could be circulated from a thermostat (Townsen & Mercer Ltd., England). pH measurements were made on a Beckman pH meter (Model H2). All the measurements were made at 20° and the chelates formed were studied under optimum conditions. A standard solution of gallium was prepared by dissolving gallium sulphate (α -Inorganics, U.S.A.) in dilute sulphuric acid. Purified samples of 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid were used for the preparation of the ligand solutions in double distilled water. All other reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer was used to maintain throughout a pH 4 and ionic strength 0.2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The nature of the complexes formed was studied by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹ and it was found that only one complex is formed under the conditions of study with λ_{max} at 355 nm in cases of both the chelates.

The effective pH ranges for the stable existence of the gallium chelates of 7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and 7-bromo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid were found to be 3.3–7.6 and 2.9–5.9 respectively. However, pH 4 was selected for subsequent studies, in both the chelates.

The empirical formula of the complexes in solution, was established by three different methods, the continuous variation method (using both equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions)², mole-ratio method³ and slope-ratio method⁴. The results indicate that one mole of gallium reacts with three moles of each of the reagents to form stable complexes in solution.

The stability constants of the chelates have been calculated by the mole-ratio method and the method using molecular extinction coefficient data. The values obtained by these methods are in close agreement and the mean value of $\log K = 13.5 \pm 0.2$ and $\Delta F = -18.1 \pm 0.3$ kcal/mole at 20° in case of $Ga(R_1)_3$ chelate; whereas the mean value of $\log K = 13.6 \pm 0.2$ and $\Delta F = -18.3 \pm 0.3$ kcal/mole at 20° in case of $Ga(R_2)_3$ chelate.

The stability constant and free energy of formation in cases of these chelates have been determined at a fixed ionic strength of 0.2 and pH 4, at various temperatures. The results obtained (using molecular extinction coefficient method) have been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Thermodynamic constants of the complexes at different temperatures

Temp. °C	Log K		$-\Delta F$ (kcal/mole)		ΔS (e.u.)	
	$Ga(R_1)_3$	$Ga(R_2)_3$	$Ga(R_1)_3$	$Ga(R_2)_3$	$Ga(R_1)_3$	$Ga(R_2)_3$
20	13.32	13.41	17.86	17.97	65.9	87.9
25	13.30	13.47	18.13	18.37	65.7	87.7
30	13.29	13.55	18.43	18.78	65.6	87.7
35	13.27	13.66	18.71	19.25	65.4	87.8
40	13.26	13.75	18.98	19.69	65.2	87.8
45	—	13.84	—	20.14	—	87.8
50	13.22	—	19.54	—	65.0	—

From the slope of the curve obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$ in case of both the chelates, the enthalpy changes (ΔH) associated with complexation reactions of gallium with R_1 and R_2 , calculated by the temperature coefficient method were found to be 1.44 kcal/mole and 7.78 kcal/mole for $Ga(R_1)_3$ and $Ga(R_2)_3$ chelates respectively.

Several values of ΔH were determined over the ranges of temperatures employed and these values were found to be constant. Entropy changes of the reactions have been calculated in case of both the chelates, using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation and the values of ΔS have been found to be 65.4 e.u. and 87.8 e.u. respectively for the $Ga(R_1)_3$ and $Ga(R_2)_3$ chelates.

A comparison of the values of stability constant, free energy change, enthalpy change and entropy change obtained in cases of $\text{Ga}(\text{R}_1)_3$ and $\text{Ga}(\text{R}_2)_3$ chelates reveals that the values are higher in case of $\text{Ga}(\text{R}_2)_3$ chelate and that the bromo derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid forms more stable complexes than the corresponding chloro derivative. This is in accordance with the results obtained by Tiao-Hsu Chang and co-workers⁵ and some of the results reported by us⁶⁻¹¹. It may be due to the fact that the chloro derivative is more acidic than the bromo derivative. High values of ΔS clearly indicate formation of very stable complexes. The fact that the stability constant increases with an increase in temperature in case of $\text{Ga}(\text{R}_2)_3$ formation and decreases with an increase in temperature in case of $\text{Ga}(\text{R}_1)_3$ formation, furnishes the clue that the first reaction is endothermic whereas the second complexation reaction is exothermic.

The authors are thankful to Dr. C. R. Mitra, Director, Birla Institute of Technology & Science, Pilani, for the laboratory facilities provided and to the Government of India for the award of a fellowship to one of them (B.K.A.).

REFERENCES

1. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
2. P. Job and G. R. Hebd, *Seances Acad. Sci.*, 1925, **80**, 928; *Ann. Chimie*, 1928, **9**, 113; 1936, **6**, 97.
3. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
4. A. E. Harvey and D. L. Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
5. T. H. Chang, J. T. Lin, T. I. Chou and S. K. Yang, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **11**, 125.
6. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *Chim. anal.*, 1970, **52**, 515.
7. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 1140.
8. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, **33**, 259.
9. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1050.
10. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 453.
11. Balraj K. Avinashi and Samir K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 174.

